
Digital Connectivity Infrastructure, Regional Economic Development and Healthcare Accessibility: A Discourse

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Abstract

The paper examined the implication of enhanced digital connectivity in pressing forward regional development and healthcare accessibility. It studied the transformative impact of digital networks on regional economies, infrastructures, and social dynamics. The research expounded the multifaceted impact of digital connectivity in fostering regional economic development and healthcare accessibility through the improvement of digital connectivity infrastructure, access to information and resources, and the facilitation of collaboration among regional critical stakeholders. The findings accentuated the pivotal role of digital infrastructure and policies in shaping the future course of regional economic development and healthcare accessibility with enhanced digital connectivity. The paper provided understanding for policymakers and businesses, and regional communities aimed at leveraging on digital technologies for sustainable growth and inclusive development.

Keywords: *Digital Connectivity, Digital Infrastructure, Healthcare Accessibility, Regional Economic Development.*

1. Introduction

...recent studies from beyond EU and US contexts have identified both productivity and employment gains associated with digital connectivity. Chen et al. (2020) in a study of Chinese firms over the period 1998–2007 find that high-speed internet significantly increases firm's productivity and worker's wage, albeit with the impact being larger for firms in industries with high skill intensity and for more educated workers. Hjort and Poulsen (2019), using firm-level data for 12 African countries over the period 2006 to 2014, find that fast internet availability in the observed African countries leads to employment increases in higher-skill occupations, but also employment gains (albeit of a relatively smaller magnitude) for less educated worker. The employment benefits manifest themselves through a variety of channels, such as greater firm entry in South Africa; higher firm level productivity among existing Ethiopian manufacturing firms; and by an increase in exports, on-the-job training, and use of online communication among firms in a further six African countries (Lynn et al, 2022; 117-118).

The transformer of the global economy is digitalization. Thus, Chen (2022), asserted that various factors and infrastructure have laid a solid foundation for economic and rural health care accessibility digitalization, such as high-speed Internet, the use of smartphones, the facilitation of online payments, changes in consumer behaviour, and service sector liberalization. Digitalization is disruptive to the traditional ways of doing business by introducing new digital tools, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), cloud computing, big data, and machine learning, to the market (Chen and Kimura, 2019). For instance, digitalization tends to lower market entry barriers and enable companies to tap into foreign markets that would otherwise be too difficult or too costly to access. This could be realized not only by reducing transaction and delivery costs, but more importantly, through greater international diffusion of information that allows firms to explore new markets globally.

Ahmed and O'Connor (2022) maintained that in today's era of globalization and technological advancement, digital connectivity has emerged as a fundamental driver of regional development. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected through digital networks, regions across the globe are leveraging this connectivity to stimulate economic growth, foster social inclusion, and spur innovation. The proliferation of digital infrastructure, including broadband internet, mobile connectivity, and digital platforms, has revolutionized the way regions engage in commerce, governance, education, and social interaction. Essentially, Knight (2015) noted that greater participation in the digital economy provides a game changing opportunity to diversify and strengthen regional economies. Effective, integrated planning for the delivery of high-speed digital connectivity and the development of digital capability – at a regional level – is critical to achieving this.

As a corollary, digital economy is developing at an extraordinary speed. The COVID-19 pandemic has spurred such growth due to restrictions on human movement and physical contact through lockdowns and state of emergency declarations (FUKUSHIMA, 2021). Although vaccines have been developed and supplied, we might continue to be restricted in our physical contacts for a while. The void of face-to face interaction has been filled most notably by digital technology. The world has seen a surge of teleworking, online meetings, online shopping and even online concerts and theatres. Even when we purchase physically at shops, we pay with smartphones rather than with cash, which we rarely use. The pandemic has accelerated unmanned digitalized operations and communications.

‘Data Age 2025’ predicted in 2018 that the annual size of the Datasphere – the sum of the world’s data --would grow from 33 zettabytes in 2018 to 175 ZB in 2025 – multiplication by fivefold. This represents an explosion of data traffic from diversified origins and formats. With the pandemic, the size of the data traffic has, no doubt, increased much more than the original prediction made in 2018. For this quantity of data to flow without problems, we need reliable and resilient digital infrastructure and governance frameworks.

This paper proposes a convincing vision for regional digital growth, where stronger interactions of enhanced digital connectivity infrastructure generate regional economic growth and rural health care accessibility through increased exposure to the digital economy. This idea canvasses and calls for the development of a strategic planning framework that will deliver regional digital economic growth and rural health care accessibility, embodied by a series of regional ‘digital connectivity infrastructure.’ The study will also explore the diverse dimensions of the role of digital connectivity in enhancing regional economic and health care accessibility development, shedding light on its transformative potential and implications for policymakers, stakeholders, and regional communities.

2.0 Conceptual Clarification

2.1 Digital Connectivity

The definition of digital connectivity is widely debated. These definitions range across a socio-technological spectrum. For example, it can be defined as the relations enabled via digital media technologies (Ponzanesi, 2019) or as the deployment of broadband infrastructure and its quality (Digital Economy and Skills Unit, 2018). In many respects, both definitions are too narrow. The former does not allow for technologies other than digital media while the latter emphasizes only one type of connectivity, broadband. Digital connectivity, as the term suggests, cannot be characterized in isolation but rather needs to be viewed as part of a wider digital ecosystem. It needs to accommodate a constantly evolving technology base and a wide range of use cases and contexts. As such, Lynn, Rosati, Conway, Curran, Fox and O’Gorman (2022) use the term ‘Infrastructure for Digital Connectivity’ (IDC) which means the availability and access to infrastructure for using digital technologies. It is used rather loosely to define digital infrastructure that connects people, business, communities and countries (FUKUSHIMA, 2021). He noted that, the Japan-EU Partnership on Sustainable Connectivity and Quality Infrastructure signed on 27 September 2019 identified digital connectivity as ‘a powerful enabler of inclusive growth and sustainable development, including digital and data infrastructure as well as policy and regulatory frameworks.’ Furthermore, it acknowledges that digital connectivity is the base that digital economy depends on and includes ‘an open, free, stable accessible, interoperable, reliable and secure cyberspace, and data free flow (FUKUSHIMA, 2021).

According to Chen (2017, 2019), when considering digital connectivity, one needs to think of the following four types of links which are data connectivity; logistics; financial connectivity; and seamless links between the cyberspace and the physical parts of the network (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Framework of Digital Connectivity

Source:Chen (2020).

According to Lynn, et al (2022), the global economic and social interactions have become increasingly organized around digital information networks that connect people, processes, things, data and networks. They posited that digital connectivity therefore is a prerequisite for participating in a networked “knowledge economy”. In the concept of economic, digital connectivity brings together businesses and consumers through a web of sophisticated information and communication technology (ICT) applications, such as cloud computing, supply-chain and business-to-business networks (Canzian et al., 2019). However, the impact of digital connectivity extends far beyond the economic sphere. For example, the potential societal benefits of digital connectivity are well illustrated in an EU context, where the European Commission has emphasized digital connectivity as a component of the European Pillar of Social Rights, a set of principles outlined by the European Commission in November 2017 which aims to ensure that EU citizens enjoy equal opportunities and access to the labour market, fair working conditions, and social protection and inclusion. To this end, the European Commission (2021) made case for the availability, security and performant sustainable digital infrastructure as one of the four pillars of the EU’s plans for Europe’s digital transformation by 2030.

Okano-Heijmans (2020) identified ‘the three practical elements of digital connectivity to include telecommunications infrastructure, business and regulation’ which are intertwined and embrace a whole spectrum of challenges. Challenges we face today are further complicated by the balance we must strike between business potential digital technology offers and state and human security issues that can be undermined, depending on the reliability of communication networks and regulations.

2.2 Rural Community Health Care Accessibility Digitalization

The 2030 Sustainable Development Goals highlight the need for everyone to receive the quality health services they need without any financial hardship (Yamey, Shretta, Binka, 2014). Hence, Erku (2023) maintained that achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC) entails making significant progress on efficient, accessible, quality and equitable health services, while ensuring financial risk protection. Primary health care (PHC), which first came to the fore with the 1978 Alma Ata declaration, provides the programmatic engine for UHC in most contexts and countries (Erku, 2023). While the COVID-19 pandemic has

resulted in global disruptions in the provision of essential health services including those provided at the PHC level (World Health Organization (2021), the public health measures put in place (e.g., lockdown, social distancing) have forced to shift the paradigm of service delivery model and provided an opportunity to accelerate the adoption and implementation of digital health solutions (Bruining, 2021).

Digital health is an overarching term that comprises eHealth (e.g., telemonitoring, tele and video- consultations, mHealth, electronic health records) and emerging technologies, including the use of computing sciences in the fields of artificial intelligence, big data, and genomics (Erku, 2023). The World Health Organization (WHO) defined electronic health (eHealth) as the use of information and communications technology (ICT) in support of health and health-related fields, including health care services, health surveillance, health literature, and health education, knowledge, and research (World Health Organization, 2021).

The digital health infrastructure and its integration into PHC services vary greatly among countries, often influenced by the economic status, health priorities, and technological advancements of a region (Erku, 2023). Notably, the increasing ubiquity of mobile devices and internet connectivity offers a unique opportunity to leverage digital health solutions even in resource-constrained settings. Recent data indicate that more than 8 in 10 people in developing countries own a mobile phone, and nearly half the global population uses the Internet (WHO, 2021; WHO, 2023). This widespread accessibility to digital platforms underscores the potential reach and impact of digital health interventions. Several countries have proactively responded to this rapidly evolving digital landscape. Approximately 87% of the World Health Organization member states have developed national policies or strategies geared toward eHealth, telemedicine, or the broader domain of digital health (WHO, 2021). However, the degree of implementation and maturity of these strategies differ widely. While some countries boast advanced digital health ecosystems with comprehensive integration of electronic health records and telemedicine services, others are in the nascent stages, piloting innovative solutions tailored to their unique contexts. Factors such as internet penetration, mobile device accessibility, and data protection regulations play a pivotal role in shaping these digital health strategies. Recognizing the transformative potential of digital health, many international organizations and stakeholders are collaborating to bolster the digital health capacities of countries, especially in low- and middle-income regions.

According to Erku (2023), the accelerated adoption of eHealth and mHealth platforms and the rapid change in the access to digital technologies have created a tremendous opportunity to expand the reach, quality, and efficiency of PHC service delivery and achieve UHC. Health systems can leverage advances in ICT to improve and maintain the continuity of service delivery post-COVID-19, such as by strengthening health management information systems and optimizing the functionality of shared electronic health records. Digital technologies also play an important role in advancing the core PHC tenet of a people-centered and integrated health service delivery model and community empowerment by improving information flows between patients and health workers, thereby shifting the nature of the patient-provider relationship (Erku, 2023). The WHO recently published a framework of e-Health for improved health service delivery (WHO), describing the potential contributions of e-Health to each of the health system attributes (i.e., service quality, efficiency, equity, accountability, sustainability, and resilience) at different levels—the individual, the service provider, the health-care organization, and the overall health system. In addition, newly emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and drones, have opened exciting possibilities and new avenues to improve the quality and accessibility of PHC services. However, without proper regulation and legislation, digital technologies may

result in potentially harmful effects (e.g., mental illness in children associated with the digital revolution) and potential for worsening existing inequities (Ziebland, Hyde, Powell, 2021).

3. The Impact Enhanced Digital Connectivity on Local Economic Development

The economic impacts of digital connectivity on regional development are profound and multifaceted. Ahmed and O'Connor (2022) discussed these as follow:

Enhanced digital connectivity facilitates greater access to markets, information, and resources for businesses in remote or underserved regions. This increased accessibility can lead to heightened competitiveness and efficiency, as companies can more easily engage in e-commerce, access online tools for marketing and management, and connect with suppliers and customers globally. Consequently, businesses in these regions may experience improved productivity and growth opportunities, contributing to overall economic development.

Digital connectivity fosters innovation and entrepreneurship in regional economies. With access to online resources, educational materials, and networking platforms, aspiring entrepreneurs and small businesses can overcome traditional barriers to entry and access valuable knowledge and support networks. This can spur the development of new industries, products, and services within regional economies, driving job creation and economic diversification. Additionally, digital platforms enable collaboration and knowledge-sharing among entrepreneurs, researchers, and institutions, facilitating the exchange of ideas and the emergence of innovative solutions to regional challenges. Digital connectivity has the potential to attract investment and talent to previously overlooked regions. As businesses seek cost-effective locations with access to skilled labor and supportive infrastructure, regions with strong digital connectivity and a conducive business environment become increasingly attractive investment destinations. This influx of investment and talent can stimulate local economies, create employment opportunities, and catalyze further infrastructure development, establishing a virtuous cycle of growth and prosperity.

It is important to recognize that disparities in digital connectivity can exacerbate existing inequalities between regions. While some areas may benefit from robust digital infrastructure and extensive online resources, others may struggle with limited connectivity and digital literacy. Addressing these disparities requires targeted policies and investments to expand access to digital technologies, improve digital skills training, and promote inclusive economic development strategies. By ensuring that all regions have equitable access to the opportunities afforded by digital connectivity, policymakers can harness its transformative potential to promote balanced and sustainable regional development.

4. The Enablers of Digital Connectivity

First, the development of e-commerce demands more stable and affordable internet connections at higher speeds. Second, the digital society is a combination of physical space and cyberspace. For instance, while e-commerce allows people to do business online, logistics are still needed to deliver the traded products. Therefore, logistics is still a compulsory part of digital connectivity. In addition, obstacles posed by poor quality roads, incomplete road and railway networks, inadequate ports, and energy supply issues will hinder the development of the digital economy. Third, the financial sector will play an unreplaceable role in the resource allocation of the digital economy, even in a cashless society. Fourth, when thinking of digital connectivity as an integrated ecosystem, there is a need to link up

different parts of the network and smoothen its overall function (Chen, 2022).

While policy overwhelmingly focuses on the deployment and quality of telecommunications infrastructure, and specifically broadband, when referring to digital connectivity, this reflects a first world and macro bias. Lynn, et al (2022) consequently believed in the assumption of uninterrupted power supply. Over 770 million people worldwide do not have access to electricity, and the overwhelming majority are located in rural areas, primarily in Asia and sub-Saharan Africa (IEA, 2020). As one observer noted: “without energy, the Internet is a black hole” (Rubin, 2017).

They equally assumed that once telecommunications infrastructure is deployed, citizens and other social institutions will have access to the computing equipment and the skills to use this telecommunications infrastructure for socio-economic and healthcare development. As discussed earlier, this is demonstrated in figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Impact of Infrastructures for Digital Connectivity

Source: Shibasaki et al. (2018).

Finally, it assumes freedom to connect to the Internet. As well as inequalities resulting from the digital divide, access to the Internet may be subject to state control generally or in specific contexts (Freedom House, 2020).

Against this background, and in the context of this study, cities have critical roles to play in local economic development as:

- i. they are not only likely to have the prerequisite electricity supply but are more likely to have higher quality telecommunications infrastructure than sparsely populated areas, and
- ii. Public access to computer equipment and the Internet through civic buildings, libraries, Internet cafes etc. Table 1 below briefly summarizes key terms and concepts with respect to Infrastructural for Digital Connectivity (IDC). For the most part, IDC comprises increasingly mainstream technologies e.g., fixed broadband, 2G–4G wireless networks, and Wi-Fi.

From the foregoing however, frontier technologies such as solar photovoltaic energy are providing greater access to power in remote areas (UNCTAD, 2021), while Next Generation Access (NGA) technologies such as 5G and Artificial Intelligence (AI) are dramatically increasing the availability and quality of broadband access. Furthermore, block chain technologies are being deployed to enable distributed and shared broadband (Messié et al., 2019; Haleem et al., 2018).

Table 1: Key Terms and Concepts in Infrastructure for Digital Connectivity

S/N	TERMS	DESCRIPTION
1.	2G	The second generation of wireless networks designed to improve on analogue with digital circuit-switched solutions (Gartner, 2021). 2G services typically support data rates of 9.6 kilobytes per second (Kbps), 14.4 Kbps and up to 64 Kbps.
2.	3G	The third generation of wireless networks. 3G wireless networks support peak data rates of 144 Kbps at mobile user speeds, 384 Kbps at pedestrian user speeds and 2 megabytes per second (Mbps) in fixed locations (peak speeds).
3.	4G	4G is the fourth generation of broadband cellular network technology that supports high peak data rates; handover between wireless bearer technologies; Internet Protocol (IP) core and radio transport networks for voice, video and data services; and support for call control and signaling (Gartner, 2021). 4G can support peak data rates of 100 Mbps in wide area networks (WANs) and 1 gigabyte per second (Gbps) in fixed or low mobility situations (Gartner, 2021).
4.	5G	5G is the fifth generation technology standard for broadband cellular network technology, and is characterized by a step change in data rates, latency, massive connectivity, network reliability, and energy efficiency (Shaf et al., 2017). It targets maximum downlink and uplink throughputs of 20 Gbps and 10 Gbps (Gartner, 2021).
5.	Broadband	A term applied to high speed telecommunications systems, i.e., those capable of simultaneously supporting multiple information formats such as voice, high-speed data services and video services on demand (European Commission, 2021b).
6.	Fixed Broadband	Fixed broadband connectivity is provided to end users via a number of wired broadband technologies, such as copper telephone lines, coaxial cables bundled with an existing television cable network, broadband over power lines (BPL), and optical fibre cables ((European Commission, 2021c). It is optical fibre cables—cables of glass fibre

		connected to end-users' homes (FTTH), buildings (FTTB) or street cabinets (FTTC)— that offer the capacity to meet anticipated future bandwidth demands (European Commission, 2021c). Optical fibre lines allow for very high transmission rates (over 100 Gbps) within a wide (10–60 kilometres) efficiency range (European Commission, 2021c).
7.	Hotspot	A hotspot is a physical location where people can access the Internet, typically using Wi-Fi, via a Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) with a router connected to an Internet service provider (Intel, 2021).
8.	Mobile Broadband	Mobile broadband is the name used to describe various types of wireless high-speed internet access through a portable modem, telephone or other device (European Commission, 2021b).
9.	Municipal WiFi	Local networks of wireless Internet access that adhere to 802.11 technological standards and are built by or for local governments for the use of the government and the people and business in that area (Jassem, 2010).
10.	Next Generation Access (NGA)	Access networks which consist wholly or in part of optical elements and which are capable of delivering broadband access services with enhanced characteristics (such as higher throughput) as compared to those provided over already existing copper networks (European Commission, 2021b).
11.	Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity Certification mark issued by the Wi-Fi Alliance to certify that a product conforms to the 802.11b, g and standards for WLANs (Gartner, 2021).

Source: Lynn, et al (2022).

However, far-reaching digital advances can bring great economic and societal benefits but can also see certain social groups and regions that are left behind. The challenge facing policy makers therefore in the coming years will be to ensure that no-one is left disconnected.

The above brief analysis reveals complex and diverse challenges concerning digital connectivity. While we rely heavily on digital means such as the Internet, and have done so particularly during the COVID 19 pandemic, it is crucial to improve computing capacity, to reduce power consumption and to minimize latency in order to ensure stable data transmission and to stay connected.

5. The Effect of Digital Connectivity on Local Economic Development— Financial Connectivity and Inclusivity

Digital technology has changed the nature of interdependence. Digital infrastructure offers opportunities for people, communities and businesses to take full advantage of convenience offered. Chen (2022) argued that financial inclusiveness should also be considered in digital connectivity. According to the World Bank (2019) cited in Chen (2022), by the end of 2017, a significant number of adults aged 15 and above still do not have a bank account. Moreover, like other aspects of connectivity, wide gaps persist in countries' readiness to adopt and use digital payments. Table 2 shows the values of the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) Fintech E-payment Readiness Index of AMS as well as their scores in each sub-index based on available data.³ Singapore is the best positioned in e-payment development, with a value of 59.6, while Viet Nam scores 22.9 at the other end. The wide dispersion of e-payment readiness exists mainly in the regulatory and policy environment and in innovative products and services.

Table 2: E-payment Readiness in Developing Region of ASEAN

Cluster	Country	ERI	ERI Components			
			Regulatory and policy environment	Infra-structure	Demand	Innovative products and services
Cluster 1: Advanced e-payment ecosystems	Singapore	59.6	93.9	59.7	37.9	57.4
Cluster 2: Transitioning e-payment ecosystems	Malaysia	44.5	80.7	41.6	27.4	38.2
	Brunei	37.2	46.6	42.4	37.4	19.6
Cluster 3: Nascent e-payment ecosystems	Thailand	29.7	33.1	37.5	23.8	23.5
	Indonesia	28.8	43.4	29.2	17.8	29.9
	Philippines	26.4	32.8	31.4	20.5	21.2
	Viet Nam	22.9	28	28.3	20	14
(Degree of dispersion)		12.8	25.8	10.9	8.3	14.7

ERI = E-payment readiness indicator.

Source: RMIT and TRPC (2015) cited by Chen (2022:147).

Online transactions – payments for either online or offline business – is one of the most dynamic areas of the digital transformation. They can be made via various payment methods (credit cards, direct debit, invoices, or online payment providers such as PayPal and Alipay). As Figure 2 shows, both the size and the number of users of online transactions have grown over time. The COVID-19 pandemic has not interrupted this tendency despite the economic shocks it has caused. According to Chen (2022), the online transactions market in ASEAN was projected to reach \$290 billion by the end of 2021, with more than 400 million users (www.statista.com). The COVID-19 pandemic has caused a stark contrast through the boom in e-wallets and the rapid shrinking of cash on delivery, especially in populous countries like Indonesia and the Philippines.

Figure 3: The Size and the Number of Online Transactions Users in ASEAN

ASEAN = Association of Southeast Asian Nations, CoD = cash on delivery.

Source: Chen (2022:148).

Internet financial innovations come with opportunities and challenges. In general, financial technology or fintech tends to be a market changer and creates new opportunities for leapfrogging development. The process of digital adoption in finance can be market-driven and self-enforced. Secure and reliable e-payment systems will increase financial inclusiveness and make digitalization more beneficial to middle- and low-income households. Policy efforts at the regional level, such as establishing industrial standards and harmonizing regulations, could help the economy realize economies of scale and support the market development (Chen, 2019; Kimura et al., 2019).

6. Policy Frameworks and Regulatory Mechanisms for Promoting Digital Connectivity

There is an onus on policymakers to respond to the inequalities that arise due to the emergence of new digital technologies and, indeed, to use new technologies to bridge existing economic, health care delivery and societal “digital divides”. The crafting of such digitally-informed economic, social, and regional policies has become all the more pertinent in the post-pandemic context. 5G mobile access networks are expected to have a greater impact than previous network shifts, enabling new classes of advanced applications, fostering business innovation and spurring economic growth (IHS, 2019).

Policy frameworks and regulatory mechanisms play a crucial role in promoting digital connectivity, ensuring equitable access to information and communication technologies (ICTs) across communities. Essentially, Ahmed and O'Connor (2022) discussed the areas of the government, development partners and other critical stakeholders’ intervention to include the following.

- i. Firstly, governments need to establish clear policies that prioritize digital infrastructure development, including broadband networks and mobile connectivity. These policies should outline targets for expanding coverage, improving speeds, and reducing the digital divide between urban and rural areas. Regulatory mechanisms should foster competition among service providers while ensuring consumer protection and fair pricing, encouraging investment in digital infrastructure.
- ii. Secondly, governments should develop frameworks that incentivize private sector participation in expanding digital connectivity. This can be achieved through public-private partnerships (PPPs) that leverage government resources and expertise with private sector innovation and investment. PPPs can help accelerate the deployment of broadband infrastructure, especially in underserved areas where the market alone may not be sufficient to meet demand. Additionally, regulatory mechanisms should provide incentives such as tax breaks, subsidies, or streamlined permitting processes to encourage private sector investment in digital infrastructure projects.
- iii. Thirdly, policy frameworks must prioritize digital inclusion, ensuring that marginalized communities and underserved populations have access to affordable and reliable digital services. This requires targeted interventions such as subsidies for low-income households, community broadband initiatives, and digital literacy programs that empower individuals with the skills to fully participate in the digital economy. Regulatory mechanisms should also mandate universal service obligations (USOs) for service providers, requiring them to extend coverage to remote and disadvantaged areas where market forces alone may not be enough to justify investment.
- iv. Finally, governments need to adopt flexible and adaptive regulatory frameworks that can keep pace with rapid technological advancements and evolving market dynamics. This includes frameworks that encourage innovation and experimentation while

safeguarding consumer rights and privacy. Regulatory bodies should engage stakeholders from government, industry, academia, and civil society to develop policies that strike a balance between promoting competition and ensuring the public interest. By continuously evaluating and adjusting regulatory frameworks in response to changing circumstances, governments can create an enabling environment for digital connectivity to thrive, driving economic growth, social inclusion, and sustainable development.

7. Concluding Remarks

As people rely more heavily on digital communication, digital connectivity must be robust with fail safe mechanisms of redundancy so as not to suddenly disrupt people's lives, be it through subsea cable or mobile networks. In addition, digital connectivity must not rely solely on one conduit, that of a certain political system or ideology nor permit data surveillance to undermine human rights and privacy.

Further to the above, Chen (2022) referred to digital infrastructure – both hardware and software – as the key to connectivity. In terms of digital connectivity, the region needs to make substantial efforts on (i) improving connectivity infrastructure in both the physical world and cyberspace, (ii) rule setting to support a development-friendly ecosystem for digitalization, and (iii) combining countries' national strategies and regional collaboration to eliminate institutional barriers.

Given the wide development gaps amongst AMS, it is critical to support latecomers to catch up faster. In this regard, the issue of capacity building needs particular attention. Digital infrastructure obstacles may come from capacity and resource limits – either capital or technology or both. The public sector may still need to take the lead to initiate and drive the increase in the supply of public goods in both quantity and quality. Private sector involvement will be equally important to make the development sustainable.

Regarding the establishment of a regulatory system to support the development of the digital economy, the most critical step is to realize free flow of data with trust. Since restrictions on data flows could harm international trade in a similar way to trade protectionism, ASEAN needs to eliminate this threat to free trade and collaborate in promoting digital adoption to sustain regional development. The related rules and regulations should cover traditional trade issues (e.g. tariffs and non-tariff measures, trade facilitation, consumer protection, and intellectual property rights) as well as new issues (e.g. cross-border information flow, privacy protection, data localization, and source code disclosure).

The ongoing Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) negotiations touch upon a wide range of issues related to regional economic development and rural health care accessibility digital connectivity. Reaching agreements on these issues will require countries to balance the interests of the economy, society, and national security, as well as the long-term gains and short-term costs. This, again, calls for collaboration amongst governments and private sector involvement.

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